

By Edwin Amuga

The Nature, Culture, and Future of Work

Introduction

Work is one of the basic components of human civilization that drive its advancement and can be defined as the activities and labor necessary for the survival and growth of a society. Work is essential in the provision of basic physical needs of food, shelter, and clothing. Work is ever developing with changes taking place worldwide in an accelerated fashion in the face of technological development and changing needs and wants. The character of civilization is determined by the nature, form of work and the position of workers in the society, which is, in turn, shaped by a society's economic, political and cultural characteristics. Work is a world comprised of all interactions between workers and employers, organizations, and the work environment, which is marked by constant cultural, political, economic, and technological change adaptations. Professions and occupations in the current world were developed from the division of labor. Work is an essential part of human history and culture. All the advancements made by humanity over the ages can be solely attributed to work. This paper aims to delve into its nature as part of human culture. The paper considers work as any activity that produces something of value to a person.

Nature of work

The definition of work depends on the historical setting. In prehistorical times, work could be defined as activities necessary for survival, as people worked to live. In the

contemporary context, the definition changes to paid employment and exchange of services for money. In the modern sense, work is necessary for survival as, through it, people can acquire food, shelter, clothing, and education (Air 1:34-46:82). Work can be looked at as paid employment defined as the exchange of money for services. The definition of work in the future may change depending on the need for human engagement in production. Generally, work can be defined as any activity that produces something of value to a person. The definition reflects more on the general nature of work as it broadens the work scope and emphasizes the social context the bargain between wage and effort takes place.

From an organizational perspective, work activities are essential as they are necessary for the production of products and services. However, from an individual's viewpoint, work is critical for the acquisition of necessities and improved living standards. Work, therefore, serves many functions for an individual. Work serves an economic purpose. Secondly, work also serves a range of social roles as the workplace provides opportunities for social interaction and friendship development. Third, work is a source of social status as one is regarded on the standards of importance basis. Work represents a source of social integration and differentiation. Work is also a source of self-esteem and identity and a means of self-actualization. Through work, people find a sense of purpose and establish their societal value and contribution. Self-esteem development is achieved through work in many ways, including the opportunity to demonstrate competence and mastery of the environment and selves. It also reassures individuals that their services are of great value to others and making the situation better (Schwartz 2015).

Work serves several useful functions in an individual's life. It provides economic self-sufficiency, social status, self-esteem, social interchange, and social identity. Without work, one would experience alienation conditions characterized by a sensation of normlessness,

powerlessness, and meaninglessness (Pursuit 1:90). By participating in work activities, individuals feel a sense of belonging as they take part in making the society a better place, failure to which one will experience isolation. With work, one finds meaning to life in their day-to-day activities, especially when the work is challenging. The inability to find work challenging makes individuals lose interest in work and, as a result, jeopardize productivity and organizational effectiveness.

History, culture, and development of work

Traditionally, humans engaged in hunting and gathering, fishing, and agriculture of food as major economic activities. As early as 40,000BCE, humans started organizing themselves in groups to track and kill animals, work their fields and fish. Other members of society remained naturally suited to gather food. Women did not participate in hunting due to the requirements of pregnancy and nursing. However, they took part in gathering and agriculture to increase the food value yield. Agricultural cultivation soon replaced gathering as its yields surpassed the supply from gathering. This progress freed some people to embark on emerging economic activities such as crafting of pottery, textiles, and metallurgy, which allowed for the division of labor. Some of the people in this society also embarked on making tools and weapons for hunting and agriculture.

The need to feed the growing population increased led to further innovation, such as the use of copper and bronze in tool making. The advancement gave birth to mining as an economic activity as they also laid the groundwork for a more complex society that could support the growing population. A revolutionary change in the nature of work was born as markets and towns were established for better trade that paved the way for the development of more

specialized occupations in commerce, defense, medicine, and law. The increasing complexity of these professions in the face of a growing population and increased conflict required a permanent record of history, events, and expertise, which fostered bookkeeping and writing development.

The earliest civilization and the later societies of Rome and Greece saw the development of class structures that were hierarchical and hereditary. The rising conflict and population pressures gave birth to Chiefs, Emperors, Kings, and Nobles that ruled these societies (Ciulla 2000). They strengthened the need to recognize boundaries and prevalence of peace as warriors supported them, and priests served as government officials. Merchants, on the other hand, purveyed products made by artisans and craftsmen, peasants worked in their family farms as slaves were made to work in craft shops and mines. The workshops formed the basis upon which modern factories are built, producing metallic tools and weapons with a few workers directed by master craftsmen. The construction of larger projects such as aqueducts and pyramids, walls, fortresses, palaces, and cities were directed by master builders who acted as foremen and scribes. The work required the mobilization of large groups of workers consisting of slaves and artisans.

The disintegration of empires such as the Roman Empire in Rome and the Egyptian Kingdom in the face of increased population, conflict, and climate change resulted in the loss of some of the organizational skills developed over time as social life contracted into smaller, self-enclosed spheres. Large tracts of land were owned by Nobles bound by inheritance. The farms were farmed by peasants who gave up a significant part of their produce to the Nobles for military protection. The medieval economy was significantly contributed to by the church that offered work to carvers, masons, and glaziers.

Town life continued to thrive as craft guilds became essential to peak in the 14th Century. Their main work was to control production and supply labor in a profession. The guild members were ranked according to their level of expertise: Apprentices, journeymen, and masters. The enormous prospects promised by the trading of raw materials and finished products led to the guild structure's disintegration as many embarked on trade abandoning their pursuit of traditional crafts. The apprentices and journeymen also pursued better prospects by being a class of free laborers. They discovered they could secure higher profits by refusing to promote journeymen into the master class. This growth paved the way for the establishment of an employer-employee relationship witnessed today.

Wind and water power harnessing that started around 1000CE began to replace or assist human laborers in olive pressing, grain processing, tanning, and bellow operation in mines and blast furnaces. These developments were among the first instances of work mechanization, which had little effect on large construction projects as churches and castles continued to be built by craftsmen directed by a master mason who designed the building.

The current economic life was founded on technological advancements and worldwide exploration as some guild masters expanded their practices from accumulating massive amounts of capital. The expansion forced the less successful masters to become wage laborers. From the developments, monopoly, the evolution of finance and trade, and machine development like the steam power in the 18th Century were born. The early factories sought ways to shorten the time required to produce an item through the division of work previously performed by a single craftsman to low-paid unskilled and semiskilled workers who were assisted by machines. This change also resulted in a reduction in production cost and item quality improvement. Laborers

who controlled production rebelled and created the necessity to install a more complex supervisory hierarchy than that seen in the preindustrial management.

The factory system grew with large cities and urban centers, which demanded increased agricultural productivity through fertilizers, mechanization, and scientific breeding practices. The use of standardized parts and extensive labor division born of the development of machine tools in the 19th Century enabled the production of many quality goods. This growing need supported the growth of manufacturing firms that demanded more specialized managers, supervisors, clerks, accountants, technicians, salespeople, scientists, engineers, and many other positions of today (Ciulla 2000).

The continuing trend towards work professionalism and specialization in industrial nations kindled new occupational discipline development such as workers' motivation, physical comfort, technological and productivity system efficiency, and science application to industry. Some of these disciplines include system engineering, research, and development, Industrial relations, production management, operation research, and human resource management.

The future of work

The past centuries have been marked by industrial and agricultural developments that have seen work transform from the historical work of hunting and gathering to business, factory, and organizational work of the twenty-first Century. In light of these revolutionary developments, the future of work is predictable as efforts have always been in place to make work easier and even rid humans of work. The nature of work is already changing as artificial intelligence, globalization, robotics, and automation continue to shift comparable to the one witnessed during the mechanization of work in the previous generations of manufacturing and

agriculture (Future 1:20-45-80). These developments, along with the adoption of artificial intelligence and workforce expansion, are shaping work. These changes raise essential questions around the skills required for future jobs, the quality of the jobs. The workplace, workforce, and the nature of work could face unavoidable revolutionary changes (Levinson 2012). Economists and technologists have warned that labor market data reveal signs of increased work automation with robots doing most of the jobs handled by human beings today. The existing models predict a world where humans do the least of work while robots drive the economy. Therefore, the future of work is certain as self-driving cars and drones being developed are most likely to replace millions of workers in the transport and manufacturing industries as well as business, medicine, and education. This forecast is shown by the trend that machines' capabilities are already formidable and growing as human capability remains the same (Shell 2018).

Despite the present anxiety on the potential destruction of current jobs driven by changes in technology and globalization, the anticipated sharp drop on overall employment seems unlikely as new jobs will be created with the paradigm shift. The growing concerns on the quality of the new jobs suggest that there will be an increase in worker disparities. The lag workforce segments are unable to benefit from the opportunities generated by the economy. They will further result in a future of work with increased discontent, and more profound social cleavages with negative ramifications of well-being, productivity, growth, and social cohesion.

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